

Insect resistance

Some gall midge-resistant rice hybrids in northeast Thailand

Weerawooth Katanyukul, Wanit Yaklai, and Suchin Chantarasa-ard, Rice Entomology Branch, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Thailand

Gall midges annually cause severe damage to rice in northeast Thailand, especially along the Mekong River. That damage, coupled with poor sandy soils, lowers rice yields. Insecticidal applications are economically impractical. Farmers object to currently available

varieties that are resistant to the gall midge (e.g., RD 4 and RD 9) because of their susceptibility to certain diseases and their unacceptable cooking qualities. Further investigation is needed to obtain desirable hybrids.

In 1975, 15 lines of rice hybrids were screened out of 60 lines. During the 1976 rainy season those 15 lines, with susceptible and resistant checks, were tested in a farmer's field at Piboonmangsaaharn, Ubonratchatani province, where annual gall-midge infestations are heavy.

Damage caused by the gall midge in

19 entries ranged from 0.8% for BR 1030-28-2 to 31.4% for RD 1, the susceptible variety (see table). Only two lines of the new hybrids were susceptible. However, many lines that showed little damage, produced very few panicles and consequently gave low yields. BR 1031-3-4-3 and BR 1031-7-5-4, from the cross BKN 6517-63-4-3/RD 9, showed a high level of gall midge resistance, a good plant type, a good number of panicles, and high yields. They also exhibited high resistance to brown spot. At heading stage, little to no brown spot infection was found on them although RD 9 and MN 62 M were heavily infected. These two lines are long grained, nonglutinous, and about 80 to 100 cm tall. They are taller than RD 4 and RD 9, which are grown in northeastern Thailand. Since local farmers like the tall plant type, BR 1031-3-4-3 and BR 1031-7-5-4 offer good promise as a substitute for RD 4 and RD 9 for gall midge resistance in northeast Thailand.

Infestation by the gall midge of rice end yield performance of gall midge-resistant hybrids at Piboonmangsaaharn, Ubonratchatani, Thailand.

Cultivar ^a	Damaged tillers (%)	Panicles (av. no./hill)	Yield (t/ha)
BR 1030-12-1	1.2	3.3	0.93
BR 1030-16-2	1.8	4.6	1.05
BR 1030-18-1	1.9	3.6	0.93
BR 1030-26-2	3.5	6.4	0.90
BR 1030-26-3	1.3	5.1	1.41
BR 1030-26-4	3.0	5.8	1.52
BR 1030-28-2	0.8	3.5	1.07
BR 1030-51-2	2.1	4.4	1.08
BR 1030-100-2	7.3	6.5	1.38
BR 1031-3-3-3	21.3	7.4	1.45
BR 1031-3-4-3	3.6	7.4	1.65
BR 1031-6-3-2	26.3	6.5	1.46
BR 1031-7-5-4	1.5	8.0	1.40
BR 1031-16-1-6	1.4	9.7	1.58
BR 1031-16-1-8	6.3	9.4	1.47
MN 62 M (R check)	3.6	4.9	2.05
RD 1 (S check)	31.4	8.5	1.09
RD 4 (R check)	6.8	8.5	1.53
RD 9 (R check)	3.7	9.3	1.37

^aBR 1030 = BKN 6625-109-1/RD 9; BR 1031 = BKN 6517-63-4-3/RD 9.

Some promising gall midge-resistant rice varieties at an Indian hot spot

U. K. Nanda, Jr., entomologist; and A. Roy, rice breeder, Regional Research Station, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Chiplima, Sambalpur (Orissa), India

The gall midge *Pachytiplosis oryzae* severely damages the main rice crop (May to November) in Sambalpur district of Orissa, India. Breeders since 1968 have incorporated into high yielding varieties a degree of resistance to the insect. Three varieties that attracted attention are RPW.6-17, RPW.6-13, and Sakti. Researchers in various centers have

Yield and silver shoot count of selected rice cultivars in a trial for gall-midge resistance. Orissa, India, 1973-75 wet seasons.

Designation	Parentage	Silver shoots (no./sq m)			Yield (t/ha)		
		1973	1974	1975	1973	1974	1975
ORS.461	Leung 152/IR8/2	7	22	21	4.47	1.97	3.04
RP.9-10-3-2-1-1	IR8/W.1251	9	7	1	3.76	1.33	2.56
RP.352-28-1-14	Eswarakora/IR8	9	3	3	1.42	2.20	2.40
ORS.261	Leung 152/IR8/2	10	11	7	2.34	3.01	2.16
RP.350-57-1-1	820862/820916	5	5		3.02	3.04	1.71
RP.352-25-2-1-1	IR8/Ptb 18//Eswarakora/IR8	2	9	7	1.09	0.81	1.50
13231	IR8/W.1263	96	20	40	2.59	0.32	1.38
RP.352-63-6-1-2	IR8/Ptb.18//Eswarakora/IR8	21	38	2	2.29	0.55	1.31
RP.351-9-1-1	820862/820851	12	14	4	0.93	0.78	1.12
2	Ptb 10/IR8	40	40	40	2.32	1.42	1.02
12754	IR8/W.1257	89	75	74	2.34	0.98	0.97
ORS.112	Leung 152/IR8/2	0	3	185	3.40	2.75	0.64
Jaya (susceptible check)		251	364	450	0.41	1.13	0.69

developed cultivars from resistant donors like W.1257, W.1263, Ptb 18, Ptb 21, and Leuang 152 but have not achieved consistent resistance and yield.

In 3 years of wet-season trials, more than 70 varieties from various parts of India have been tested and a number have been found promising (see table).

The rice brown planthopper and its predator, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, on some rice cultivars in India

T. M. Manjunath, B. S. Naidu, and N. K. Krishna Prasad, Regional Research Station, V. C. Farm, Mandya (Karnataka), India

In a varietal trial of 27 rice cultivars during kharif 1976, hopperburn was noted in November in mature grains. Examination revealed the presence of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal. and its predator, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter.

Both insects were found on all the cultivars and the predator was found invariably associated with the pest. The number of planthoppers varied from 5 to 133/sq m with a mean of 45 ± 6 ; that of the predator, from 37 to 423/sq m with

Brown planthopper predator, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*.

a mean of 187 ± 25 . The hopperburn was noted in only one of three replications with the variety IET 3229 indicating, as did observations in several farmers' fields, that the pest infestation was highly localized and that in the absence of natural enemies the insects would have caused much more crop damage.

The *Cyrtorhinus* population was about four times the planthopper's, and the population varied together ($r = + 0.88$).

The present data support the statement of Manjurath et al., who reported that until the crop flowered, the brown planthopper population generally exceeded that of the predator, but as the crop neared harvest, the situation reversed.

Cyrtorhinus seems a promising predator. We have developed methods for mass-rearing it in the laboratory, and for making inundative, timely releases in brown planthopper-infested fields to evaluate its value as a biological control agent.

List of scientists in brown planthopper research

E. A. Heinrichs, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

At the brown planthopper symposium held at IRRI 18–22 April 1977, a preliminary list of scientists involved in research on the brown planthopper was developed. The list includes 103 names and addresses of scientists from 13 countries. Research areas listed are taxonomy; migration; surveillance and forecasting; biogeography; flight behavior; bionomics; varietal, breeding resistance; physiology; ecology; chemical, biological, cultural, and integrated control.

To obtain a copy of the list, write the Entomology Department, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Populations of *Nilaparvata lugens* and *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* on and yields of selected rice cultivar. Mandya, Karnataka, India, kharif 1976.

Cultivar	Yield (kg/plot) ^a	<i>N. lugens</i> (no./sq m)	<i>C. lividipennis</i> (no./sq m)
IET 1444	4.61	68	268
IET 2222	4.13	11	54
IET 2662	4.26	11	41
IET 2707	4.03	68	261
IET 2742	3.56	29	53
IET 2914	3.21	57	295
IET 2924	3.76	48	343
IET 2967	3.81	13	43
IET 3116	4.39	15	45
IET 3279	3.86	12	37
IET 3325	3.92	55	273
IET 3331	3.43	33	85
IET 3626	4.48	63	268
IET 3629	4.57	57	315
IET 3630	4.34	95	350
IET 4111	3.95	53	228
IET 4112	4.00	59	223
IET 4554	2.85	70	333
IET 4556	4.09	133	288
IET 5704	4.49	24	113
IET 5857	4.41	26	105
IET 5858	4.63	5	79
IET 5859	3.75	8	67
Ratna	4.26	101	372
Cauvery	4.30	90	423
IET 5860	4.20	15	43
MR 272	5.41	7	53
Mean	4.10	45	187
SE _m		6.5	24.9
F test	*	NS	NS
CD (0.05)	1.10		
CV (%)	16.2		

^aPlot size = 6.75 sq m.

*Significant at 5% level.